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Assessment of Entrepreneurship Skills for the Sustenance of Mechanical Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Contemporary Rivers State Society.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the assessment of entrepreneurship skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary Rivers State society. Specifically, the study sought to: identify the technical proficiency skills and problem solving skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary Rivers State society. Two research questions and two hypotheses were answered and tested at .05 level of significance. A descriptive survey design guided the study. The population of the study comprised 45 lecturers and 23 technologist in the three tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient. The reliability coefficient achieved was .98. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and to ascertain the homogeneity of responses, while z-test was used to test the hypotheses. The study found that understanding design principles and methodologies to create new products, skill in creating prototypes using Computer Aided Design software and hand on fabrication techniques, among others, knowledge of production methods and material to effectively design and produce items, the ability to analyze and diagnose problem, the capacity to think logically and systematically, the ability to visualize and understand complex system, the ability to plan and develop creative solutions were entrepreneurship skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary Rivers State society. It was recommended that mechanical technology education students should cultivate and acquire entrepreneurship skills that can drive and enhance their employability, and drive innovations potentials for sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises.

Keywords: Mechanical Technology, Entrepreneurship Skills Medium Scale Enterprises

INTRODUCTION

Mechanical Technology (MT) is an essential aspect of Technical Education (TE), which has been introduced to address the growing demands of skilled professionals in various societies and industries in the world. As the world continues to advance technologically, the need for individuals with a strong foundation in Mechanical Technology has increased significantly. This has led to a growing interest in entrepreneurial skills among Technical Education students pursuing careers in Mechanical Technology, in mechanical technology programme, several skills are provided such as plumbing, welding and fabrication, vulcanizing, wheel alignment, valve grinding, wheel balancing, auto electrical, auto body repair, spray painting, engine maintenance, auto body building, brazing, threading, turning, drilling,

milling, grinding, cutting, knurling, riveting, shaping, galvanizing, soldering, chamfering, beveling, hammering, forging, and casting, among others. Technical Education is often viewed as a facilitator of entrepreneurship skill development, as it equips students with specialized knowledge and skills that can be applied to real-world problems and challenges (Nwoye, 2011). Technical Education, with its role plays a vital role in preparing students for entrepreneurial careers (Lidimma, 2012). Entrepreneurship has been defined as the process of identifying, developing, and bringing a vision to life (Dyke et al., 1992). Entrepreneurship has been recognized as a crucial factor in driving economic growth and innovation.

Aminu (2009) posited that the success of an entrepreneur is dependent on factors such as determination, leadership quality, creativity, self-nurturing, self-discipline, energy, and future orientation. Lidimma (2012) emphasized the role of entrepreneurs as givers of employment, providers of infrastructures, and valuable services to the community. Therefore small and medium scale enterprises (SME) are widely considered as the pillar of many economies globally, thereby contributing to employment, innovation, and economy growth in societies in Rivers State. Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) play a vital role in fostering economy growth and development, particularly in local and regional context. The effectiveness of marketing strategy is essential for (SME) to succeed and strive in an increasingly competitive market. According to Olalekan & Ajibola (2020), effective market strategies can influence customer acquisition, retention, and overall business growth. Akinyele (2019), Marketing strategies refer to the approaches and techniques employed by businesses to reach, attract, and retain customers. For SMEs, marketing strategies might include traditional methods. Such as word-of-mouth and media advertising, or more modern digital marketing procedures which includes WhatsApp, Telegram, twitter, and email marketing. Understanding of these strategies is crucial for improving the performance of SMEs (Kato & Olorunfemi, 2021). Therefore, mechanical technology education lecturers should cultivate entrepreneurship skills that can drive student's technical proficiency skills for small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary rivers state society.

Statement of Problem

Due to the lack of understanding of principles, and the vast opportunities in the field of MT that can earn students self-reliance and even make them employers of labor after graduation, they rather pursue white-collar jobs that are not readily available, disregarding the vast opportunities provided by the Mechanical Technology program in Technical Education institutions. Despite the high expectations of society for MT graduates to become self-reliant, their performance is diminishing. Elisha, (2014). Innovation attributed this to several challenges, including the high cost of tools and equipment needed for setting up metal workshops, a high percentage of metal workshops are operating with obsolete tools and equipment, inadequately trained technical instructors, insufficient funds for consumables materials, and inadequate workshop facilities. This could be the reason why some graduates, including mechanical Technology Education graduates are still unable to secure employment. Attesting to this, Amaechi, et al., (2017) lamented that graduates in different fields of technical and vocational education and training including mechanical technology education are roaming the streets of Nigeria as a result of lack of relevant skills needed for the Sustenance Mechanical Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Contemporary Society. Therefore, with the enormous problems resulting from unemployment of graduates due to lack of adequate skills, it is necessary to carry out a research on the skills relevant for employment in modern industries. Based on this the researcher considered it fit to investigate the Assessment of Entrepreneurship Skills for the Sustenance of Mechanical Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Contemporary Rivers State Society.

Purpose of the Study

Specifically, the study:

1. Examine the technical proficiency skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary rivers state society.
2. Determine the problem solving skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary rivers state society.

Research Questions

1. What are the Technical Proficiency Skills for the Sustenance of Mechanical Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in contemporary rivers state society?
2. What are the Problem Solving Skills for the Sustenance of Mechanical Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in contemporary rivers state society?

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The area of the study was Rivers State. The population of the study was 68, comprising 45 lecturers and 23 technologist in the three tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Therefore, the researcher believes that lecturers and technologist was more equipped with the relevant information for this study. As at the time of this study, there are three tertiary institutions in Rivers State offering mechanical technology education, such as Rivers State University (RSU), Port Harcourt, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) and Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku. Respectively. Due to the fact that the population was small and manageable, the entire population was used and there was no sampling method adopted. Therefore, the study was a census study. A self-made survey questionnaire titled "Assessment of Entrepreneurship Skills Questionnaire" (AESQ), served as the instrument for data collection. The instrument was face validated by two experts in the Department of Vocational and Technology Education in Rivers State University, Port-Harcourt and one from Department of Measurement and Evaluation in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku. Also, the reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient tool. The coefficient value obtained was .98 and was used to judge the reliability of the instrument. Copies of the instruments was administered and retrieved by the researchers at the spot of administration. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research question and to test homogeneity of responses while z-test was used to test the hypotheses. Mean scores < 3.00 was disagreed, while mean values equal or greater scores ≥3.00 was agreed. Also, calculated hypotheses values less than table values was agreed while calculated hypotheses equal or greater than table values was disagreed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Research Question 1

What are the technical proficiency skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary rivers state society?

Table 1: Mean Responses on Assessment of Technical Proficiency Skills for the Sustenance of Mechanical Small and Medium Scale Enterprises

S/N	Technical Proficiency Skills	Technologist (n ₁ =23)		lecturers (n ₂ =45)		Mean Set	Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	\bar{x}_2	SD ₂		
1	Understanding design principles and methodologies to create new products	4.00	1.28	4.00	1.21	4	Agree
2	Skill in creating prototypes using cad software and hand on fabrication techniques	3.54	1.71	3.94	1.34	3.74	Agree
3	Knowledge of production methods and material	4.36	1.28	3.88	1.33	4.12	Agree
	effectively design and produce items					4.12	
4	The ability to analyze and diagnose problem	4.11	1.37	3.94	1.46	4.03	Agree
5	The capacity to think logically and systematically	4.04	1.60	4.04	1.27	4.04	Agree
6	The ability to visualize and	4.36	1.13	3.90	1.47	4.13	Agree

	understand complex system						
7	The ability to plan and develop creative solutions	4.11	1.52	4.44	.82	4.28	Agree
8	The ability to use mathematics to solve problems	4.36	1.19	4.43	.90	4.40	Agree
9	The ability to use the computers for technical task	4.04	1.50	4.57	.70	4.31	Agree
	Grand Mean	4.10	1.40	4.13	1.17		

Table 1 on the mean responses for technical proficiency skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary rivers state society. Shows that lecturers and technologists agreed that all the items highlighted are Technical Proficiency Skills for the Sustenance of Mechanical Small and Medium Scale Enterprises, this is based on the grand mean scores of 4.10 and 4.13 respectively which are above the 3.00 stated as the acceptable mean.

Use the computers for technical task are the technical proficiency skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary rivers state society.

Research Question 2

What are the problem solving skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary rivers state society?

Table 2: Mean Responses on the Assessment of Problem Solving Skills for the Sustenance of Mechanical Small and Medium Scale Enterprises

S/N	Problem Solving Skills	Technologist (n ₁ =23)		lecturers (n ₂ =45)		Mean Set	Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	\bar{x}_2	SD ₂		
10	Understand the needs and constraints of end users to create users centered designs	3.14	1.18	3.38	1.12	3.26	Agree
11	Learn to interpret data and use it for decision making	3.75	.97	3.16	1.28	3.46	Agree
12	Assess the pros and cons of different solution using criteria like feasibility cost and time	3.57	1.23	3.46	1.11	3.52	Agree
13	Use calculus, algebra, and statistic to solve technical problems	3.50	1.29	3.43	1.06	3.47	Agree
14	Familiarity with CAD software to visualize and analyze design	3.57	1.17	3.31	1.19	3.44	Agree
15	Group projects to enhance collaboration and integrate diverse perspective	3.36	1.25	3.35	1.19	3.36	Agree
16	Learn to scope projects, set milestones, and allocate resources effectively	3.54	1.07	3.26	1.28	3.40	Agree
17	Evaluate how solutions impact society, the						Agree
	environment, and economies	3.39	1.26	3.47	1.30	3.43	
18	Keep up with the latest developments in mechanical technology and industry standards	3.79	1.20	3.60	1.26	3.70	Agree
	Grand Mean	3.51	1.18	3.38	1.20		

Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 on the problem solving skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary rivers state society. Shows that lecturers and technologists agreed that all the question Q10-18 highlighted above are the problem solving skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary rivers state society. This is based on the grand mean scores of 3.51 and 3.38 respectively which is above the 3.00 state as the accepted mean. Which found that understand the needs and constraints of end users to create users centered designs., learn to interpret data and use it for decision making., assess the pros and cons of different solution using criteria like feasibility cost and time., use calculus, algebra, and statistic to solve technical problems., familiarity with CAD software to visualize and analyze design., group projects to enhance collaboration and integrate diverse perspective., learn to scope projects, set milestones, and allocate resources effectively., evaluate how solutions impact society, the environment, and economies., keep up with the latest developments in mechanical technology and industry standards are the problem solving skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary rivers state society.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean score of technologist and lecturers on the Technical Proficiency Skills for the Sustenance of Mechanical Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in contemporary rivers state society.

Table 3: z-Test for Responses on the Assessment Technical Proficiency Skills

Categories	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Technologist	23	4.10	1.40	94	.09	1.98	Not Significant
Lecturers	45	4.13	1.17				

Table 3. Shows that the grand mean score and standard deviation scores of technologist was 4.10 and 1.40 respectively. Also, the grand mean scores of lecturers was 4.13 and 1.17 respectively. The z-calculated (z-cal) value was .09, while the z-critical (z-crit) was 1.98 at a .05 level of significance for two tailed test. This result shows the z-cal of .09 is less than z-crit of 1.98 which means that the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there was no significant difference between the mean score of technologist and lecturers on the automated turning operation skills for assessment of Entrepreneurship Skills for the Sustenance of Mechanical Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Contemporary Rivers State Society.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean score of technologist and lecturers on the problem solving skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary rivers state society.

Table 4: z-Test for Responses on the Assessment Problem Solving Skills

Categories	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Technologist	28	3.61	1.21	94	.70	1.98	Not Significant
Lecturers	68	3.42	1.21				

Table 4 shows that the grand mean score and standard deviation scores of technologist was 3.61 and 1.21 respectively. Also, the grand mean scores of lecturers were 3.42 and 1.21 respectively. The z-calculated (z-cal) value was .70, while the z-critical (z-crit) was 1.98 at a .05 level of significance for two tail test. From the result, the z-cal of .70 is less than z-crit of 1.98 which indicates that the null hypothesis was accepted. Basically, there was no significant difference between the mean score of technologist and lecturers on the assessment of entrepreneurship skills for the sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary rivers state society.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions was drawn: that for the Sustenance of Mechanical Small and Medium Scale Enterprises, students require understanding design principles and methodologies to create new products, skill in creating prototypes using CAD software and hand on

fabrication techniques, knowledge of production methods and material to effectively design and produce items, the ability to analyze and diagnose problem, the capacity to think logically and systematically. The ability to use mathematics to solve problems, the ability to use the computers for technical task, the ability to work collaboratively with others technicians and professionals. It was also recommended & learn to interpret data and use it for decision making, assess the pros and cons of different solution using criteria like feasibility cost and time, use calculus, algebra, and statistic to solve technical problems, familiarity with CAD software to visualize and analyze design, group projects to enhance collaboration and integrate diverse perspective, learn to scope projects, set milestones, and allocate resources effectively, evaluate how solutions impact society, the environment, and economies, keep up with the latest developments in mechanical technology and industry standards among others that mechanical Technology education students should cultivate and acquire entrepreneurship skills that can drive and enhance their employability, and drive innovations potentials for sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises in contemporary rivers state society.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Mechanical technology education students should cultivate and acquire entrepreneurship skills that can drive and enhance their employability, and drive innovations potentials for sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises.
2. Technical education students should enhance their ability to tackle complex technical challenges and innovate solution that are effective and sustainable for sustenance of mechanical small and medium scale enterprises.

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